

Immunogenomics Review

The purpose of the immunogenomics review is to confirm that the results of the ImmunoNX pipeline are correct. This process involves checking if the output contains the correct files, reviewing quality control (QC) metrics, creating a written report, presenting results to a panel of experts, and using visualization tools: **IGV** and **pVACview**, to manually verify the neoantigen candidates. These steps help ensure that high confidence neoantigen candidates are selected.

Initial review of ImmunoNX Pipeline Outputs

At this stage, we mostly want to confirm that the pipeline succeeded and that transferring the data files into the case folder on our local server was successful. Check the total number and total size of files. In order to proceed, the following files must be present: tumor/normal DNA BAMs, RNA BAM, annotated variants VCF for pVACseq, proximal variants VCF, annotated variants TSV, HLA typing results, QC report files, and pVACseq/pVACview results file.

Creating an Immunogenomic Review Report

For our vaccine clinical trials, we have found creating a document to organize notes during the Immunogenomics Review is helpful because the review is a very manual process. These instructions outline how to create a similar report. After verifying that the data files look relatively normal. The structure of this report also provides a roadmap of how to conduct a manual review of candidates.

The structure of this report is:

1. Introduction: a brief description of the patient's history, where the data comes from, and/or what results are expected.
2. Files Used: a list of Google Bucket paths (or local paths if the final outputs will be stored locally) pointing to the files used for pVACview and IGV.
3. Basic data QC Review: QC metrics used to evaluate basic data quality.
4. FDA Quality Thresholds: QC metrics described in clinical trial FDA documentation.
5. HLA allele review: A comparison between HLA allele predictions between different algorithms and (if included) clinical HLA typing. This is important because we do not want to predict candidates for alleles that are not in the patient.
6. Review of multi-algorithm support for strong binding affinity: A description of the predicted binding affinity of candidates of interest. This section contains detailed notes of the review done using pVACview.
7. Tumor type / driver variant review: What variants we expect to see and if they are known to drive tumor progression. These will be important neoantigen candidates to prioritize.
8. Fusion review: Fusion candidates that need further review.
9. Comparison to orthogonal variant calls: a comparison of the pipeline's variant calls to another source of variant information (if included).

[!NOTE] Give examples or figure out what to call these variants

11. IGV review: This section is dedicated to the final stage for visually verifying the candidates of interest in IGV. Often this section functions as a conclusion for the immunogenomics review. It details how

many candidates were reviewed, which candidates got rejected and why, and other interesting or concerning things of note from the case.

We have created several scripts to aid in the generation of these lists of metrics

Generating a Report to summarize QC Metrics

To generate a report evaluation of the case's basic QC metrics, run the following commands

```
cd $WORKING_BASE

docker run -it --env HOME --env WORKING_BASE -v $HOME/:$HOME/ -v
$HOME/.config/gcloud:/root/.config/gcloud
griffithlab/neoang_scripts:latest /bin/bash

python3 /opt/scripts/get_neoantigen_qc.py -WB $WORKING_BASE -f
final_results --yaml $WORKING_BASE/yamls/$CLOUD_YAML
```

Generating a Report to summarize QC Metrics

The following set of QC values can be obtained from the QC report tables generated by the pipeline and are used to determine whether the case meets certain data quality criteria.

To generate a table evaluating the case's QC metrics, run the following commands:

```
cd $WORKING_BASE

docker run -it --env HOME --env WORKING_BASE -v $HOME/:$HOME/ -v
$HOME/.config/gcloud:/root/.config/gcloud
griffithlab/neoang_scripts:latest /bin/bash

python3 /opt/scripts/get_FDA_thresholds.py -WB $WORKING_BASE -f
final_results
```

[!WARNING]

Include what the FDA metrics look like

Generating a Table to summarize HLA predictions

To generate a table with the predicted normal and tumor HLA alleles, run the following commands

```
cd $WORKING_BASE

docker run -it --env HOME --env WORKING_BASE -v $HOME/:$HOME/ -v
$HOME/.config/gcloud:/root/.config/gcloud
griffithlab/neoang_scripts:latest /bin/bash
```

```
python3 /opt/scripts/hla_comparison.py -WB $WORKING_BASE
```

Presenting Results in a Tumor Board Setting

As mentioned in the publication, the first stage of the Immunogenomics Review is a presentation of candidate neoantigens for selection by an Immunogenomics Tumor Board (ITB). This is mainly performed using pVACview. Most files needed to conduct this review are produced by the ImmunoNX pipeline and saved as results. These consist of:

- pVACview .R application files matched to the version of the results files
- \$sample-name.all_epitopes.aggregated.tsv (Class I)
- \$sample-name.all_epitopes.aggregated.metrics.json (Class I)
- \$sample-name.all_epitopes.aggregated.tsv (Class II)
- Cancer Gene List in TSV format with Genes in the first column

Before the ITB meeting. Load these files in pVACview and make sure everything is working.

During the meeting the "Evaluation" column will be used to mark each Pending candidate as Accept, Review, or Reject until sufficient candidates have been identified (some lower priority candidates may remain Pending). Once the case review is complete use the Export functionality to save the candidates and selections in both TSV and Excel format. These will be the **ITB Reviewed Candidates** that will be used during the following steps of the review.

ITB Evaluation Criteria

The following sections describe the criteria considered during immunogenomics tumor board meetings, provide examples, define Accept/Reject criteria where possible and enumerate special cases and exceptions.

Set Clonal DNA VAF

Based on the tumor DNA VAF of known drivers and/or consideration of the distribution of tumor variants you may choose to adjust the Clonal DNA VAF and "Recalculate Tiering" before beginning the review. For example, if the tumor has a TP53 or KRAS driver variant with a VAF of 25% and you believe it represents a heterozygous (non-CNV altered region) you might set this cutoff to 25%.

Variant Type

Consider whether the variant is a SNV, InDel or DNV. Variants that are insertions, deletions or nucleotide variants have different interpretations from the perspective of DNA and RNA VAF, reference matches, number of core binding peptides expected, etc.

TSL (transcript support level)

Take note if the TSL is > 1 or NA. Even if the candidate would otherwise be marked Accept it should be marked as **Review** and support for the specific transcript used to annotate the predicted amino acid change should be evaluated using the tumor RNAseq data. TSL values greater than 1 or NA are often acceptable and simply reflect incomplete annotation of the transcripts of a gene (an ongoing, partially manual, curation process). It can be helpful to refer to the "transcript table" in Ensembl where additional

annotation tiering information is available. For example, it is possible for a transcript to have a TSL > 1, but for that transcript to also be categorized as MANE Select, GENCODE Primary or Ensembl Canonical, any one of which would increase confidence in the quality of the transcript annotation. A screenshot of an example Ensembl transcript table is provided below for reference:

Transcript ID	Name	bp	Protein	Biotype	CCDS	UniProt Match	RefSeq Match	Flags
ENST00000275493.7	EGFR-201	9905	1210aa	Protein coding	CCDS5514	P00533-1	NM_005228.5	MANE Select Ensembl Canonical GENCODE Primary GENCODE Basic APPRIS P1 TSL:1
ENST00000450046.2	EGFR-205	9700	1157aa	Protein coding	CCDS84105	C9JYS6	-	GENCODE Basic TSL:4
ENST00000455089.5	EGFR-206	3844	1091aa	Protein coding	CCDS87507	Q504U8	-	GENCODE Basic TSL:1
ENST00000344576.7	EGFR-203	2872	705aa	Protein coding	CCDS5515	P00533-3	-	GENCODE Basic TSL:1
ENST00000342916.7	EGFR-202	2239	628aa	Protein coding	CCDS5516	P00533-4	-	GENCODE Basic TSL:1
ENST00000420316.6	EGFR-204	1570	405aa	Protein coding	CCDS47587	P00533-2	-	GENCODE Primary GENCODE Basic TSL:1
ENST00000700145.1	EGFR-211	1418	344aa	Protein coding	-	A0A8V8TPW8	-	CDS 5' incomplete TSL:3
ENST00000459888.2	EGFR-207	2407	No protein	Protein coding CDS not defined	-	-	-	TSL:3
ENST00000463948.1	EGFR-208	561	No protein	Protein coding CDS not defined	-	-	-	TSL:3
ENST00000700146.1	EGFR-212	3827	No protein	Retained intron	-	-	-	-
ENST00000700144.1	EGFR-210	2165	No protein	Retained intron	-	-	-	-
ENST00000700147.1	EGFR-213	1701	No protein	Retained intron	-	-	-	-
ENST00000485503.1	EGFR-209	665	No protein	Retained intron	-	-	-	TSL:4

Pos (Position)

Evaluate whether the variant is at an anchor site. If it is potentially at an anchor site, review the anchor heatmap view below. If the variant is at an anchor, require that the wild type be a weak binder (> 500 nm, ideally weaker than that). If the peptide is marked as Anchor Residue Fail in the "Transcript Set Detailed Data" view (the peptide and HLA listed under Anchor Residue Fail column will be highlighted red) then mark the candidate as **Reject**.

Prob Pos (Problematic Positions)

In past testing it has been observed that peptides containing cysteines may result in difficulties during synthesis, due to disulfide bond formation, or have reduced stability during storage. Thus, peptides containing cysteines may later fail identity/purity tests during drug product testing.

For most studies using a synthetic long peptide approach for vaccine delivery, if any position in the core binding peptide has a cysteine, our group marks the candidate as **Reject**. Some long peptide vaccine studies allow some amount of cysteines in the synthesized peptide (e.g. 1 - 2 in the long peptide sequence) and may attempt to mitigate the potential issues above (e.g by strategic pooling, such as avoiding multiple cysteine containing peptides in the same pool). You may need to clarify if Cysteines need to be excluded by contacting your peptide manufacturer.

For studies using DNA/RNA vectors for vaccine delivery, no problematic amino acids should be defined in the input YAML file, and this criteria can be ignored.

Num Passing Peptides

This is not an **Accept / Reject** criterion but a larger number of passing peptides is desirable, as is often the case for frameshift neoantigen candidates. Note that the number of peptides reported as Passing in pVACview and aggregated reports depends on the thresholds selected. Relevant pVACtools parameters include: - *-binding-threshold* , - *-percentile-threshold* ,

- *-allele-specific-binding-thresholds* and - *-top-score-metric*.

IC50 and %ile MT (median mutant peptide binding affinity prediction)

The median IC50 should be less than 500 nm or the median percentile less than 1% for an Accept. Exceptions are sometimes made if: (a) the variant is a known cancer driver, (b) elution algorithms (e.g.

BigMHC_EL, MHCflurryEL Presentation, NetMHCpanEL) have a score with <1.0 %ile, (c) if there is disagreement between prediction algorithms and some predict that it is a strong binder (particularly NetMHCpan and MHCflurry as these algorithms have performed well in benchmarking exercises.

RNA Expr (gene expression estimate)

The gene expression estimate should be >1 TPM for an Accept. A rare exception that might be evaluated during genomics review is when the RNA VAF and RNA coverage of the specific variant allele is strong but the gene expression was <1 TPM.

RNA VAF (RNA variant allele fraction)

An RNA VAF > 0 is generally required for an Accept. Higher is better. A low VAF may indicate sub-clonality or allele specific expression. If the RNA depth is high, the DNA VAF is acceptable but if the RNA VAF is low (e.g. $< 5\%$) then Reject (evidence of allele specific expression favoring the wild type allele). In rare cases, exceptions may be made if: (a) the variant is a known driver, (b) the gene is expressed at a high level; or (c) the low RNA VAF may be explained by lower coverage for technical reasons (e.g., in a region suffering from end bias).

Allele Expr (Allele Expression)

This metric is the product of the RNA VAF and Gene Expression value. We have generally required a minimum Allele Expression value of 3 for Accept. Exceptions are sometimes made and a lower value is accepted in the 1 - 3 range, if the DNA VAF indicates that the variant is subclonal but it is otherwise a strong candidate.

RNA Depth

This is not an Accept/Reject criterion but the value is used to interpret the RNA VAF. For example, if RNA Depth < 10 , the RNA VAF estimate is not very robust. Low RNA depth reduces confidence that the variant was actually detected.

If the total number of variant allele supporting RNA reads is small (e.g. < 5), IGV review should be used to carefully assess the quality of this small number of reads. The number of unique cDNA fragments supporting the variant should be examined (e.g. if the supporting RNA count is 2, it is possible that there is just 1 unique cDNA fragment, sequenced in both directions).

In the case of small numbers of supporting RNA reads, the alignments of these reads should be examined to confirm that they are consistent with a mRNA sequence. For example, if the RNA reads containing the variant are spliced across introns (exon-exon junctions) this would represent stronger support than if they are contained within an exon. Similarly, if the RNA-seq data was generated in a strand-specific way, RNA reads containing the variant that also match the expected expression strand would represent stronger support than if they have the incorrect strand. If RNA reads containing the variant are not correctly spliced (e.g. span into the intron instead of connecting to the next exon) these should not be considered supporting the variant even though they contributed to a non-zero VAF.

DNA VAF

By definition DNA VAF must be > 0 if a variant was called. The accuracy of a DNA VAF estimate depends on the depth of reads covering the variant position.

A higher DNA VAF is preferable because it suggests higher tumor clonality. A higher DNA VAF can also result if the variant allele has been amplified or is affected by loss-of-heterozygosity (LOH). For example, if a heterozygous variant arises in a tumor and the chromosome (or a region of it) that harbors the variant is duplicated, this can result in higher DNA VAF. This scenario is also desirable from the perspective of neoantigen prioritization.

A lower DNA VAF is less desirable because it could indicate a sub-clonal variant (i.e. one that is not present in all the cells of the tumor). Low DNA VAFs are also more likely to be false positive somatic variants, although this is dependent on the absolute depth of sequencing achieved. If the sequence error rate of the platform is low, and the depth is high, somatic variants can be robustly identified down to low VAFs (e.g. 1 - 2 %). A default conservative threshold for allowing somatic variant calls is often set at 5 % but may be lowered to 1.5 - 2.5 % in cases where tumor purity is low.

Correct interpretation of individual DNA VAFs generally must consider multiple factors including: (a) purity of the tumor (aka tumor cellularity); (b) ploidy of the tumor (e.g. copy number gains/losses that may influence VAFs); (c) clonality of the variant; (d) random sampling error. A detailed discussion of these interpretations is beyond the scope of this document but many tools and publications are available.

Tier

Each neoantigen candidate variant is automatically placed into one of several tiers based on a simple heuristic: Pass, LowExpr, NoExpr, SubClonal, Poor, Anchor. The Tier is evaluated for the top peptide arising from each variant.

If the Tier is Pass, the variant can generally be accepted with limited review. However, there are a few issues that may require even a Pass candidate to be rejected including: (a) problematic amino acids (e.g. Cysteines, if defined by the user) in the core binding peptide; (b) problematic amino acids that are outside the core binding sequence but closely flanking it such that a long peptide sequence is not possible (c) reference matches, (d) other issues that come up during genomic review, including that the somatic variant giving rise to the neoantigen is a false positive.

The additional tiers (LowExpr, NoExpr, SubClonal, Poor, Anchor) are designed to draw attention to specific areas of consideration during the ITB review or genomics review.

The Poor tier indicates that either the candidate does not meet basic binding/presentation criteria or it does but has multiple other issues.

Transcript Sets

The recommended approach for pVACtools analysis is to annotate somatic variants with all possible transcript annotations according to VEP (using the `--flag-pick` option to note the top transcript consequence according to VEP but still retain the others). The result of this approach is that neoantigen predictions for a single variant can vary from one transcript annotation to another. A neoantigen may arise in an exon of one transcript (where the variant is considered missense) but be absent in another transcript if the exon is skipped (where the variant is considered intronic). Furthermore, a variant with a consistent predicted amino acid change in two transcripts may still lead to distinct short (e.g. 8 - 11 - mer) or long (e.g. 25 - 35 - mer) peptides if the variant is close to the edge of an exon and the RNA splicing of downstream/upstream exons varies. These are just two examples of the many impacts that alternative transcripts may have on neoantigen identification and prioritization. While not common, it is possible for

entirely distinct neoantigens to arise from a single somatic variant when multiple RNA transcripts are simultaneously expressed.

In pVACview, a "transcript set" defines the collection of transcripts that give rise to an identical list of predicted peptides. If more than one transcript set exists, the set producing the top single peptide candidate is automatically selected. Two transcript sets can have overlapping peptides but the overall complement of peptides from each set must differ. I.e. there must be at least one peptide sequence that is only possible in the context of one transcript set and not the other.

When multiple transcript sets are observed for a somatic variant, they should each be considered to determine whether multiple long peptides could be targeted in the neoantigen therapy. Alternative candidate peptides arising from each set must meet the usual criteria for binding, presentation, expression, transcript structure support, etc.

As a final note, all of the above functionality and guidance on alternative transcripts applies only to known alternative RNA transcripts. Somatic variants that alter RNA splicing in a tumor specific fashion can also be a rich source of neoantigen but must be analyzed by a dedicated approach (e.g. using pVACsplice).

Transcript Biotype

For the most part, neoantigen predictions should correspond to transcripts that have been assigned the Biotype "protein_coding" by Ensembl. Additional biotypes (e.g. nonsense mediated decay) may result in neoantigen peptide predictions and may be considered (rarely and

cautiously) if review of the transcript annotation, RNA-seq data or other data (e.g. Mass Spectrometry) suggests the transcript actually does produce protein. It is often helpful to review the "transcript table" in Ensembl (see example above in the TSL section).

Reference Matches

Reference Matches are an Accept/Reject criterion. Reference matches refer to one or more sequence matches between the candidate neoantigen peptide and other regions of the reference proteome (e.g. we typically compare to all known Ensembl protein sequences). The reference match analysis performed by pVACtools first attempts to identify the expected match of the mutant sequence to its corresponding wild type gene location. This result is excluded from the Reference Match result and any remaining matches to other genes or other positions within the source gene are reported.

Generally a candidate with reference matches is marked as Reject. A larger number of reference matches is considered more problematic. A large number of reference matches (e.g. > 3) is often observed when the neoantigen peptide has low complexity (e.g. contains a homopolymer stretch) or when it arises from a large gene family with a high degree of homology across family members.

Correct interpretation of Reference Matches in pVACview requires understanding of three related amino acid sequences and how they relate to each other: the Best Peptide, the Query and the Matched Peptide.

The Best Peptide sequence is the sequence that was evaluated as a neoantigen candidate (e.g. an 8 - 11 - mer mutant peptide for class I neoantigens). The Query Sequence is used to search for reference matches related to this sequence. This sequence is created by identifying the position of the mutation and adding a flanking sequence of 7 amino acids evenly to either side. The Matched Peptide is a substring of the Query Sequence. The Matched Peptide comes from an unexpected location in the reference proteome (i.e

anywhere other than the region the neoantigen Best Peptide sequence comes from). The Matched Peptide may have complete or partial overlap with the Best Peptide sequence but the overlap must contain the mutant amino acid position(s). Refer to the examples below to visualize the relationship between the Best Peptide, the Query and the Matched Peptide.

In certain circumstances a candidate with reference matches may be considered acceptable. Generally a candidate with a reference match will only be acceptable if the number of reference matches is low (e.g. 1) and the degree of overlap between the Best Peptide candidate and the Matched Peptide is limited (e.g. less than 50 % of amino acids of the Best Peptide occur in the Matched Peptide).

In the following examples, the Best Peptide sequence is in bold, the mutant amino acid is marked in red and the substring that matches between all three sequences is underlined.

Example 1 (from hcc 1395 benchmark analysis):

(A) The Best Peptide sequence is a 9-mer mutant peptide from the gene SORBS3: **APSLSPHKM**; (B) The Query Sequence is the 15-mer: APYLGSA**APSLSPHKM**. (C) The Matched Peptide is an 8-mer exact match in the gene SLC45A3: **SAPSLSPH**. Of the neoantigen peptide, 7 of 9 amino acids match exactly to the reference matching sequencing in another gene. In this example we would Reject the candidate.

APYLGSA**APSLSPHKM** - Query sequence from neoantigen gene SORBS3
APSLSPHKM - Best Peptide sequence from neoantigen gene SORBS3
SAPSLSPH - Matched Peptide sequence from unexpected gene SLC45A3

Example 2 (from hcc 1395 benchmark analysis):

(A) The Best Peptide sequence is a 10-mer mutant peptide from the gene FAM217B: **KENADEDSAG**; (B) The Query Sequence is the 15-mer: **NADEDSAGDLSDSER**. (C) The Matched Peptide is an 8-mer exact match in the gene ZFH2: **SAGDLSDS**. Of the neoantigen peptide, 3 of 10 amino acids match exactly to the reference matching sequencing in another gene. In this example we would Accept the candidate.

NADEDSAGDLSDSER - Query sequence from neoantigen gene FAM217B
KENADEDSAG - Best Peptide sequence from neoantigen gene FAM217B
SAGDLSDS - Matched Peptide sequence from unexpected gene ZFH2

The general principle of Reference Match analysis is that we want to avoid the situation where the neoepitope sequence presented to the T cell by the Best Peptide could also be presented by the reference peptide. Interpretation of this concept is often aided by referring to the Anchor Heatmap view in pVACview (see below for more details).

A known complication of the reference match analysis is that for inframe insertions and deletions, the mutant peptide will sometimes be reported as having a reference match to the same gene it derives from. This result occurs because of the ambiguity in interpreting the location of insertions and deletions, particularly where there is similarity between the inserted/deleted amino acids and the surrounding reference amino acids.

Refer to the pVACtools and pVACview documentation and tutorials for more information on the determination and interpretation of reference matches.

Class II Binding Predictions

In the case where a neoantigen candidate does not have any qualifying class I peptide predictions (no convincing MHC binding, presentation and immunogenicity), a candidate may still be Accepted based on class II MHC predictions. Relaxed criteria to Accept a candidate based on class II binding are: < 500 nm OR percentile < 2 %. Class II predictions tend to result in systematically lower binding affinity values for many class II alleles and a more conservative criteria requires the percentile to be < 2 %.

Note on class II pairing notations

In class I MHC notation, a complex is formed between each class I HLA molecule and B 2 M (e.g. HLA-B* 45 : 01 - B 2 M). However, since the involvement of B 2 M is a constant its presence is implied and it is not listed in the HLA notation. In class I, the MHC peptide binding groove is internal to the protein encoded by the HLA gene.

In contrast to class I, all class II MHC molecules operate as a dimer with the MHC peptide binding groove formed by the dimerization. Each class II complex is described as an alpha-beta pair. The three HLA genes of primary interest for class II binding and presentation are HLA-DP, HLA-DQ, and HLA-DR.

HLA-DP and **HLA-DQ** complexes have a dimer notation, explicitly listing the alpha-beta pair of each complex. Valid HLA-DP and HLA-DQ dimer notations for neoantigen analysis therefore take the form:

[HLA-DPA 1 *NN:NN - HLA-DPB 1 *NN:NN]

[HLA-DQA 1 *NN:NN - HLA-DQB 1 *NN:NN].

An individual typically has up to two alleles for DPA 1 , DPB 1 , DQA 1 , and DQB 1 . All DPA 1 alleles can pair with all DPB 1 alleles. All DQA 1 alleles can pair with all DQB 1 alleles.

Note that we have encountered algorithms that will report binding predictions for single components of HLA-DP and HLA-DQ genes (only alpha or only beta). Such predictions are difficult to interpret and should be ignored.

Example HLA types for the HLA-DP gene: Patient 1. DPA 1 * 01 : 03 , DPA 1 * 02 : 01 DPB 1 * 04 : 02 , DPB 1 * 14 : 01

Valid pairings: DPA 1 * 01 : 03 - DPB 1 * 04 : 02

DPA 1 * 01 : 03 - DPB 1 * 14 : 01

DPA 1 * 02 : 01 - DPB 1 * 04 : 02 DPA 1 * 02 : 01 - DPB 1 * 14 : 01

Example HLA types for the HLA-DQ gene: Patient 1. DQA 1 * 01 : 01 , DQA 1 * 01 : 02 DQB 1 * 05 : 01 , DQB 1 * 06 : 02 Valid pairings: DQA 1 * 01 : 01 - DQB 1 * 05 : 01

DQA 1 * 01 : 01 - DQB 1 * 06 : 02

DQA 1 * 01 : 02 - DQB 1 * 05 : 01 DQA 1 * 01 : 02 - DQB 1 * 06 : 02

In the case of **HLA-DR** genes, by convention, only the beta component is listed because HLA-DR alpha is not functionally variable across individuals (i.e. the HLA-DRA component is constant/implicit). Valid HLA-DR dimer notations for neoantigen analysis therefore take the form: DRB 1 *NN:NN, DRB 3 *NN:NN, DRB 4 *NN:NN and DRB 5 *NN:NN. An individual typically has up to two alleles for the DRB 1 gene and up to two alleles drawn collectively from the DRB 3 / 4 / 5 genes.

Example HLA types for the DR genes: Patient 1. DRB 1 * 07 : 01 , DRB 1 * 14 : 07 DRB 3 * 02 : 02 , DRB 4 * 01 : 03

Patient 2. DRB 1 * 03 : 01 , DRB 1 * 15 : 01 DRB 3 * 01 : 01 , DRB 5 * 01 : 01 Patient 3. DRB 1 * 01 : 01 , DRB 1 * 15 : 01 DRB 5 * 01 : 01

Types of peptide:MHC prediction scores

Several types of prediction scores have been described as relevant to pMHC prioritization. Included among these are distinct concepts: binding, stability, cleavage, transport, processing and immunogenicity. A description of the rationale behind each of these types of algorithms is far beyond the scope of this document, but in very simple terms:

- **Binding** (aka binding affinity) algorithms (e.g. NetMHCpan, MHCflurry) directly model the binding of a short peptide sequence to the class I/II MHC groove. These algorithms are typically trained on in vitro binding data generated by testing individual peptides (from peptide libraries) against individual MHC molecules at a range of concentrations to determine the concentration required to achieve 50 % displacement of a reference peptide. The score is often reported as a 50 % inhibitory concentration (IC 50) in nM or as the IC 50 percentile rank.
- MHC **stability** algorithms (e.g. NetMHCstab) predict a related but distinct aspect of the peptide-MHC complex. While binding prediction models the likelihood that a given peptide will bind to a specific MHC molecule, stability prediction models how long a peptide-MHC complex remains stable before dissociating.
- Peptide **cleavage** algorithms (e.g. NetChop) attempt to predict cleavage sites of the proteasome. These algorithms may be trained on a combination of in vitro protein degradation and observed MHC ligands. One goal for the interpretation of these algorithms is to address whether a long peptide, upon cleavage at predicted sites, will retain a core binding sequence with favorable binding/stability characteristics.
- Peptide **processing** algorithms (e.g. NetMHCpan_EL, MHCflurryEL, BigMHC_EL) are trained on peptide elution mass spectrometry data and attempt to predict, in aggregate, peptides that are bound, stable, cleaved and transported appropriately. While conceptually a superior approach compared to binding affinity predictions, training data remains limited for some/many HLA alleles.
- **Immunogenicity** prediction algorithms are a rapidly evolving area of neoantigen prioritization but are significantly limited by availability of training data. The term immunogenicity is used in many ways, and historically has been used in the context of all of the above types of prediction algorithms. However, it is most precisely described as relating to either the prediction of whether a pMHC complex will be recognizable by a TCR or more broadly whether it is capable of inducing a T cell response in a functioning host immune system. Some immunogenicity algorithms directly model the characteristics of the TCR facing residues of a peptide and these must therefore be interpreted in the context of binding and presentation predictions. Other immunogenicity algorithms attempt to model all the requirements of recognition in aggregate. Limited immunogenic true positive/negative training

data makes this last approach challenging at present. Binding and presentation may be thought of as necessary but not sufficient for immunogenicity.

Binding Affinity Algorithm Agreement (binding and percentiles scores)

High agreement in binding affinity score and percentile ranks between multiple algorithms trained on distinct data with alternative algorithmic approaches may be interpreted as providing higher confidence in a candidate (with some caveats). In general, the highest agreement between algorithms is correlated with the amount of training data available for a particular HLA allele. By contrast, low agreement between algorithms reduces confidence. In cases of low agreement, particular algorithms may be given greater weight based on published benchmarking exercises. Furthermore, in the case of poor agreement between binding algorithms, greater consideration may be given to processing (elution) algorithm scores, based on the assumption that the independent peptide elution mass spectrometry training data may provide insight.

Example with high inter-algorithm agreement (binding affinities all < 100 nM)

Example with low inter-algorithm agreement (binding affinities range from ~ 300 - 10,000 nM)

Processing (aka elution) Algorithm Scores

Processing (aka elution) algorithm scores are discussed briefly above and generally reported on a 0 - 1 scale, with higher numbers indicating a higher probability of being presented. The shape of the distribution of these scores varies from algorithm to algorithm so where possible the

percentile rank should be considered (e.g. considering a percentile score < 2 % to be acceptable).

Immunogenicity Algorithm Scores

Immunogenicity algorithm scores are discussed briefly above and generally reported on a 0 - 1 scale, with higher numbers indicating a higher probability of being recognized by a T cell. pVACtools currently supports DeepImmuno and BigMHC_IM. DeepImmuno was trained on immune validation data from IEDB, but not tumor specific immunogenicity data (citation) and predictions are available for only lengths 9 - 10 and a

relatively narrow set of HLA alleles compared to the binding and presentation algorithms. In general, Immunogenicity prediction algorithms are considered to be experimental at this stage.

Cancer Gene Status Cancer genes are often defined as those obtained from the Cancer Gene Census. However, additional review of the known relevance of the specific cancer gene to the specific type of tumor should also be considered. If a neoantigen corresponding to a cancer gene is not ranked highly, it may be given additional consideration to see if it can be accepted (e.g. relying on scores from individual binding, presentation and immunogenicity algorithms instead of median scores). Cancer Gene neoantigens should be highlighted (e.g. with green background) in the candidate neoantigen sheet and peptide order sheet.

Frameshift mutations

A single frameshift mutation has the potential to give rise to many neoantigens, depending on how quickly an alternative stop codon occurs in the alternate frame. Frameshift mutations can introduce considerable complexity to review of neoantigen candidates and selection of long peptide sequences for the vaccine design. These considerations include:

- Increased possibility of being a false positive somatic variant. Insertion and deletion somatic variants are perhaps more likely to have quality issues, particularly as the number of inserted or deleted bases increases (e.g. > 4). These variants may be subjected to additional scrutiny during manual genomic review of the supporting sequence data.
- Miscounting of RNA expression support for the variant allele. Accurately calculating the variant allele fraction (VAF) for insertion and deletion somatic variants becomes more difficult as the number of inserted or deleted bases increases (e.g. > 4). Manual genomic review of the supporting sequence data, including consideration of soft-clipped alignments that support the variant should be performed and the VAF estimate adjusted if necessary.
- Need to adjust length of frameshift sequence analyzed for neoantigens. For performance reasons we often run pVACtools with a *-downstream-sequence-length* setting of 100 amino acids. While rare, if a frameshift sequence is longer than this before hitting a stop codon, some neoantigen sequences might be missed. Frameshifts should be reviewed to determine if a stop codon is reached within the length specified by *-downstream-sequence-length*.
- Potential for nonsense mediated decay (NMD). In cases where a frameshift variant is predicted to trigger NMD (e.g. > 50 nucleotides upstream of the last exon-exon junction) the candidate may be considered lower priority, particularly if the RNA allele expression for the frameshift variant is low compared to the median VAF of all somatic variants for the tumor.
- Additional complexity of proximal variant interpretation. In-phase proximal germline or somatic variants that occur with the short/long peptide window for a neoantigen candidate may not be corrected by pVACtools. Proposed short and long peptide sequences should be investigated to confirm that the impact of any proximal variants on amino acid sequence has been correctly incorporated into the final peptide sequence.
- Frameshifts that extend the open reading frame beyond the wild type stop codon leading to a novel C-terminal tail. These candidates may be given high priority because these have potential for stable expression, avoid NMD concerns, and may lead to long sequences of tumor specific amino acids.
- Potential to select multiple distinct sequences for the vaccine design. When a frameshift variant gives rise to a long novel sequence (e.g. > 20 amino acids), it should be examined to determine if two or more distinct long peptide sequences should be targeted in the final design. Additional stretches of the frameshift sequence should be examined for qualifying class I/II targets. Multiple distinct entries

may be created in the peptide order form to reflect distinct synthesis attempts needed to incorporate each into the final design.

Example of a long frameshift peptide sequence (qualifying class I peptide regions in red):

RQKGSYLT~~HEASGLDEQGEAREAF~~LKAATDTRGKRNS~~SSDPIPTPGLGLGLGWGPPH~~CQLQ
 GTSKDIYQSLG~~WWASPP~~TTNTSDAWAGMGVLD~~AWISVRAR~~SEGPEVWVPQGAGAKGPDPPS
 PVRAVGIGLGEDN~~WGKARAPRLQ~~NQVLWGGGQFLGRVGGAGKGN~~TDF~~GGPRP

Proposed candidates:

LTHEASGLDEQGEAREAF~~LKAATDTRGKRNS~~SSDPIPTPGLGLGLGWGPPH

SSDPIPTPGL - 105.8nM - HLA-C*05:01

IPTPGLGLGL - 185.9nM - HLA-B*07:02

IPTPGLGL - 399.79nM - HLA-B*07:02

QLQGTSKDIYQSLG~~WWASPP~~TTNTSDAWAGMGVLD~~AWISVRAR~~SEGPEVWV

SLGWWASPP - 281.71nM - HLA-A*02:01

TSDAWAGMGV - 358.64nM - HLA-C*05:01

TSDAWAGMGVL - 414.48nM - HLA-C*05:01

TTNTSDAWAGMGVLD~~AWISVRAR~~SEGPEVWVPQGAGAKGPDPPSPVRAVGI

GVLD~~AWISV~~ - 39.04nM - HLA-A*02:01

VLD~~AWISVRA~~ - 425.57nM - HLA-A*02:01

RARSEGPEV - 428.96nM - HLA-B*07:02

RSEGPEVWV - 434.65nM - HLA-C*05:01

Dinucleotide mutations

When dinucleotide variants (DNVs) occur (e.g. chr 14 - 60724007 - 60724008 - GG-TT) pVACtools will automatically incorporate both nucleotide changes into the predicted short and long peptide sequences. Neoantigen candidates from these variants can be interpreted similarly to a single nucleotide variant with one substantial caveat. The VAF for these variants may not be calculated correctly for these variants in the DNA, RNA or both. Genomics review of the variant in IGV can be used to determine the correct VAF.

Anchor Heatmap examination

The anchor heatmap visualization provided in pVACview reflects an analysis approach previously described and published (Xia, et al. *Science Immunology*, 2023). A systematic computational analysis was performed to determine for each HLA allele, what positions of that allele act to anchor the peptide to the MHC binding groove. Conventional rule of thumb approaches may consider the first and last few amino acids to be anchoring and the "center" of the peptide to be TCR facing. A more specific rule of thumb may consider position 2 and the last position to be the anchor. The anchor heatmap reflects a more systematic approach where the anchor positions were determined empirically and automatically selected based on a cutoff. By default the AA positions that contribute 80 % of the anchor potential are defined as anchor positions. In practice this means that for each allele 1 - 4 positions are generally defined as anchor positions.

The anchor heatmap (see example below) displays each candidate peptide in the context of the predicted anchor sites for each HLA allele. The degree to which each position acts as an anchor is displayed as a normalized anchor score with darker blue highlighting indicating positions that contribute the most to anchoring. The mutant position is highlighted in red.

If a candidate has a mutation determined to be at an anchor position, the aggretopicity (aka differential aggretopicity index; DAI) of the candidate should be considered. If the mutation position corresponds to an anchor, and the binding/presentation of the wild-type peptide is strong, the candidate should be Rejected. If the mutation position corresponds to an anchor and the binding/presentation of the wild-type is weak the candidate may be Accepted (assuming all other criteria are met). If the mutant is not at an anchor position, the wild type binding/presentation may be ignored. Additional extensive descriptions of this assessment can be found in the pVACtools and pVACview documentation.

[!NOTE]

See more examples of how to use pVACview for neoantigen candidate review [here](#)

Genomics Review (post ITB meeting)

Once the ITB meeting is complete and the preliminary set of candidates has been nominated, a genomics review of all candidates must be completed following the procedures and criteria laid out below.

Example Location of Files Needed for Genomics Review

Variants Review Files

- **variants.final.annotated.tsv** - > used to verify that ImmunoNX variants were also called by CLE pipeline

pVACseq Review Files

- **\$sample-name.all_epitopes.aggregated.tsv** (Class I)
- **\$sample-name.all_epitopes.aggregated.metrics.json** (Class I)
- **\$sample-name.all_epitopes.aggregated.tsv** (Class II)
- Cancer Gene Census List in TSV format downloaded from Cosmic

IGV Review Files

- **annotated.expression.vcf.gz** - > ImmunoNX variant positions to load into IGV
- **normal.cram** - > Normal exome DNA alignments to load into IGV
- **tumor.cram** - > Tumor exome DNA alignments to load into IGV
- **rnaseq/alignments/MarkedSorted.bam** - > Tumor RNA-seq alignments to load into IGV
- **Ensembl 105_GRCh 38_UcscGenePred_Custom_Coding.ensGene** - > custom transcript annotation track containing only transcripts acceptable for neoantigen identification

Genomics Review Checklist/Principles

QC Metrics

The following are high level descriptions of the kinds of detailed review that should be performed following selection of candidates by the ITB

Basic data QC review. Review relatedness, contamination, FDA QC reports, and purity metrics. Note any red flags.

- Summarize **total number of uniquely mapping reads** generated for Tumor/Normal exome and Tumor RNA-seq (i.e. not counting duplicates that arise from PCR amplification of the same source DNA fragment).
- "Unique Mapped Reads" from file: `qc/fda_metrics/aligned_$sample_dna/table_metrics/$sample_dna_aligned_metrics.txt`
 - Qualitative description of these counts:
 - < 40,000,000 is poor
 - 40,000,000 - 50,000,000 is acceptable
 - 5,000,000 - 100,000,000 is good
 - > 100,000,000 is excellent
- Summarize **duplication** rates for tumor/normal DNA samples
 - "Mapped Read Duplication" from file: `qc/fda_metrics/aligned_normal_dna/table_metrics/normal_dna_aligned_metrics.txt`
 - Qualitative description of these rates:
 - > 75 % is very poor
 - 50 - 75 % is poor
 - 30 - 50 % is acceptable
 - 20 - 30 % good
 - < 20 % is excellent
- Check Somalier results for sample tumor/normal **sample relatedness**.
 - "Relatedness" column from file: `qc/concordance/concordance.somalier.pairs.tsv`
 - Qualitative description of these rates:
 - > 97.5 % is excellent
 - 95 %- 97.5 % is good
 - 90 - 95 % is concerning
 - < 90 % is very concerning
- Check VerifyBamID results for **contamination** of both tumor and normal samples
 - "FREEMIX" column from file (column 7): `qc/$sample/$sample.VerifyBamId.selfSM`
 - Qualitative description of these rates:
 - < 0.025 is good
 - 0.025 - 0.05 is concerning
 - > 0.05 is very concerning
- Check RNA-seq metrics for % **reads aligning to transcripts**
 - Find the sum of "PCT_CODING_BASES" and "PCT_UTR_BASES" from file: `qc/tumor_rna/rna_metrics.txt`

- Helpful command: "cut -f 17,18 rna_metrics.txt"
 - > 90 % excellent
 - 75 - 90 % good
 - 50 - 75 % acceptable
 - < 50 % sub-optimal
- Check for evidence of **end bias** in the aligned RNA seq data using file: [qc/tumor_rna/rna_metrics.pdf](#)
 - Visually inspect this plot. If the RNA-seq data is of good quality from intact RNA the plot should have a "horse back" shape, representing lower coverage at the beginning and end of transcripts but quickly rising and remaining relatively high over the majority of the transcript positions. RNA-seq data made from highly degraded RNA combined with polyA selection or oligo-dT cDNA priming can have a heavily biased distribution instead. Such data can still produce gene expression estimates but may be unable to effectively verify expression of some somatic variant alleles.

[!NOTE]

See examples of good and bad end bias plots in the [Troubleshooting README](#).

- Check that the correct RNA strand setting was used in the pipeline YAML file. For example, the
 - Detected strand file: qc/tumor_rna/trimmed_read_1 strandness_check.txt
 - YAML file: [workflow_artifacts/\\$case_immuno_cloud-WDL.yaml](#) (grep for "strand")
 - See further help on the [Troubleshooting README](#)
- Summarize total variants called and total neoantigen variants called (i.e. the subset of variants that could lead to neoantigens). Briefly, total variants is how many somatic mutations were detected in the tumor. Total neoantigen variants is the subset of these that lead to possible neoantigen candidates (i.e. those that cause protein coding changes in known genes). Note that the number of neoantigen candidates selected by the Immunotherapy Tumor Board will be a small subset of this number.
 - **Total variants** called can be obtained from [variants.final.ansnotated.tsv](#) (previously [pvacseq.annotated.tsv](#)). Simply the number of rows in this file minus the header.
 - **Total neoantigen variants** called can be obtained from pVACview (total candidates) or by looking at the pVACseq aggregated report file to get this number.

Tumor type / driver variant review

Given the reported tumor type do we see evidence for expected somatic driver variants? Enumerate these in the report and if there are no plausible driver variants, raise this as a possible red flag. This review can be conducted in pVACview with CancerGeneCensus genes loaded.

Other strategies for assessing drivers:

- Use the variants TSV file and select all variant types that would directly impact protein sequence
- Look for variants previously observed in COSMIC or pathogenic according to ClinVar
- Intersect the genes with these mutations with Cancer Gene Census
- Take the candidate genes that result from the previous two queries and search for these in CBioPortal after selecting studies that match the cancer type of the patient

HLA allele review for sample/data mixup Make sure the HLA alleles as being used in pVACview for the final selection of candidate match up with those expected for the case based on Optitype/PHLAT predictions from the data and clinical HLA typing results if available.

Review multi-algorithm support for strong binding affinity We are often using the “lowest” score method to prioritize candidates (the other, more conservative option would be “median”). This means the peptide with the lowest IC 50 from *any* algorithm. This leads to more candidates but can lead to the situation where a peptide is nominated and most algorithms actually predict that it is a poor binder and a minority of algorithms (perhaps only one) predict that it is a strong binder. In those cases, is the candidate still acceptable? Is there another peptide where the best score was slightly higher but there is better agreement across algorithms? ○ MHCnuggets has often been observed to be an outlier. If only this algorithm suggests a peptide is a strong binder, these candidates should probably be failed in review. ○ NetMHCpan and MHCFlurry have been reported by some benchmarking exercises as among the better performing algorithms ○ In cases where binding algorithms have high disagreement, additional weight should be given to presentation algorithms trained on peptide-elution mass spectrometry data

Compare variant results to another list of orthogonal variants

In some cases you might know other variants you are expecting to find in your data. If you specify that variant file in your YAML for your pipeline runs, check if the variant was also called by the ImmunoNX pipeline. This status is automatically provided in the “VALIDATED” column in the `variants.final.annotated.tsv` file produced by the ImmunoNX pipeline. The orthogonal variants validation status is also automatically incorporated into the Neoantigen Candidates review spreadsheet.

IGV Review

You can SMB mount to obtain access to the case data files on your local computer and create an IGV session with the following 6 components in order:

1. Final somatic variant VCF from ImmunoNX pipeline (`annotated.expression.vcf.gz`)
2. Normal exome DNA alignments (`normal.cram`)
3. Tumor exome DNA alignments (`tumor.cram`)
4. Tumor RNA-seq alignments (`rnaseq/alignments/MarkedSorted.bam`)
5. Ensembl v105 transcript annotations ([Homo_sapiens.GRCh38.105.sorted.coding.gtf](#))

Save the session file for others to use. Use this session to perform the following specific review activities and make note of the findings in the candidate review spreadsheet.

- **Somatic variant review:** For any peptide candidate being considered for inclusion in the design, manually review the underlying somatic variant in IGV to make sure it appears to be a real somatic variant. Our [published guidelines](#) can be used for this step.
- **Proximal variants review:** Check for any nearby variants that might impact prediction of the peptide sequence. Most of these should be handled automatically by pVACTools if it was run with the proximal variants option. The definition of “nearby” for the purposes of proximal variants review is any variant capable of impacting either the predicted class I epitope sequence (8 - 11 amino acids), the class II epitope sequence (12 - 18 amino acids) or the long peptide sequence that will be used for DNA/RNA vector or peptide sequencing (35 - 50 amino acids). If a variant is NOT near the edge of an exon, the proximal space to review may be up to 75 bp in either direction (potentially longer for a frameshift variant). If the variant is near the edge of an exon, the proximal space to review can be much larger as adjacent exons may be separated by large introns. Extensive analysis of the importance of proximal variants analysis has been published ([Hundal et al. Nature Genetics, 2019](#)).
- **RNA-seq allele review:** Check for expression of the allele. If the candidate was selected, but had poor read support for the mutant allele, check whether this could be explained by a local coverage or

alignment issue, where the gene is otherwise well expressed.

- **Transcript isoform review:** Check if the RNA transcript the candidate peptide is extracted from is actually expressed. Does the RNA-seq data support the expected nearby exon-exon junctions? Is there evidence for alternative splicing that might influence expression of the mutant allele or the structure of the transcript that expresses it (possibly impacting the presumed peptide sequence)? When performing this review the following IGV display settings are useful: (1) "View as pairs" and (2) "Color alignments by" - > "first-of-pair strand". Note that to perform the transcript isoform review, it will be necessary to load the correct Ensembl GTF of transcripts in IGV.

Long Peptide Extraction and Final Report Generation

Using the selected transcript, extract 51-mer peptide sequences that contain the candidate neoantigen. Annotate this sequence with the "best" class-I and class-II binding peptides. The selection of long peptide sequences should reflect the final conclusion of the ITB review and genomics review.

Use `pvacseq create_peptide_ordering_form` to create a fasta file that has the long peptide sequences needed. These files are useful in the manual review process.

An example of how this command would look:

```
export PATIENT_ID="hcc1395"

# Get the tumor sample ID from the annotated expression file
gzcat $WORKING_BASE/final_results/annotated.expression.vcf.gz | less
export TUMOR_SAMPLE_ID="hcc1395-tumor-exome"

docker run -it --env WORKING_BASE --env TUMOR_SAMPLE_ID --env PATIENT_ID -
v $HOME/:$HOME/ -v $HOME/.config/gcloud:/root/.config/gcloud
griffithlab/pvactools:6.0.2 /bin/bash

cd $WORKING_BASE/

mkdir -p manual_review

# This command generates a fasta file of 51mers for all candidates

pvacseq create_peptide_ordering_form -o manual_review/ \
    -p
$WORKING_BASE/final_results/pVACseq/phase_vcf/phased.vcf.gz \
    --pass-only -d 150 \
    --aggregate-report-evaluation Accept,Reject,Pending,Review
\
    --classI-IC50=1000 --classI-percent=2 --classII-IC50=500 -
-classII-percent=2 --prob-pos C \
    --allow-incomplete-transcripts \
    $WORKING_BASE/final_results/annotated.expression.vcf.gz 25
\
    $WORKING_BASE/itb-review-
files/HCC1395_v140rc.Annotated.Neoantigen_Candidates.tsv \
```

```
$WORKING_BASE/final_results/pVACseq/mhc_ii/*.all_epitopes.aggregated.tsv \
    ${PATIENT_ID} ${TUMOR_SAMPLE_ID}

exit
```

[!NOTE]

During a normal review process, where you accept candidates in pVACview first during an ITB meeting, you will probably only want to generate 51mers for the candidates marked "Accept" or "Review". Change the `--aggregate-report-evaluation` argument accordingly.

[!NOTE]

The `allow-incomplete-transcripts` will not be necessary for pipeline runs using pVACseq v6 or greater, which will automatically exclude incomplete transcripts.

1. Peptide Fasta

A plain text fasta file with each peptide sequence. This will be used for final blast checks and can be used with Pepstats to obtain molecular weights for each peptide for the ordering form.

1. Note that if any changes to peptides are made manually during the genomics review (e.g. to select a different reference transcript, or to correct for a complex variant or proximal variant), this file must be updated to have a one-to-one relationship with the Long Peptides Spreadsheet.
2. The starting point for this file is the `annotated_filtered.vcf-pass-51mer.fa` file produced by the `pvacseq generate_protein_fasta` tool described above.

Example location:

```
$case/generate_protein_fasta/candidates/annotated_filtered.vcf-pass-51mer.fa
```

2. Long Peptides Spreadsheet

An annotated peptide sequence file used to create the final vaccine manufacturing order form. The starting point for this spreadsheet is the `.fa.manufacturability.tsv` produced by the `pvacseq generate_protein_fasta` tool described above.

Example location: `$case/generate_protein_fasta/candidates/annotated_filtered.vcf-pass-51mer.fa.manufacturability.tsv`

The Long Peptide Spreadsheet should provide the following:

a. Peptide highlights

ClassI (red text), ClassII (**bold** text) and mutant peptides (underlined) and if using a long peptide vaccine Cysteines (C) indicated with a larger font. Please note the underline convention for these variant types:

1. SNVs - underline the single mutant amino acid
2. In-frame insertions - underline the inserted amino acids
3. In-frame deletions - underline the one amino acid to the left and one amino acid to the right of the deleted amino acid position

4. Frameshift Insertions or Deletions - underline the entire novel amino acid sequence (i.e. from where the sequence starts to diverge from wild type until the end of the peptide sequence)
5. In-frame RNA fusions - underline one amino acid on the left side of the fusion junction and one amino acid on the right side of the fusion junction
6. Frameshift RNA fusions - underline the entire novel amino acid sequence (i.e. from where the sequence starts to diverge from wild type until the end of the peptide sequence)

b. Top class I/II HLA alleles

List the best class I and class II allele separated by a "/". List the class I allele if median affinity < 1000 nm OR percentile < 2%. List the class II allele if median affinity < 500 nm OR percentile < 2%. Note that the class I/II peptide should only be red/bold if it meets these criteria.

c. Molecular weight

Get the molecular weight for each long peptide sequence by using the EMBOSS Pepstats program.

3. Reviewed Candidates Table (MHC Class I)

A spreadsheet with the reviewed class I candidates from pVACview along with any notes on each candidate. Each row corresponds to a single variant leading to potential neoantigens, with the top candidate provided. Each should include the final evaluation: Reject or Accept. Each should also include any detailed notes from the pVACview and IGV reviews that document the rationale for accepting or rejecting the candidate.

The starting point for this spreadsheet is the TSV that is exported from pVACview at the end of the review in the Immunotherapy Tumor Board meeting.

Example storage location and file naming convention: `$case/itb-review-files/mcdb047.revd.Annotated.Neoantigen_Candidates.xlsx`

4. Reviewed Candidates Table (MHC Class II)

A spreadsheet with the best class II candidate peptides. Each row corresponds to a single variant leading to potential neoantigens, with the top candidate provided.

The starting point for this spreadsheet is the class II aggregate report from pVACseq that came from the WDL pipeline (or a manual run of pVACseq if that was required).

Example storage location: `mcdb046/gcp_immuno/final_results/pVACseq/mhc_ii/mcdb046-tumor-exome.all_epitopes.aggregated.tsv`

5. Executive Report (aka Genomics Review Report)

A narrative report with an executive summary of key findings from each of the major genomics review steps above. This should be created as each step is completed. In addition to summarizing each step, note any special situations with individual candidates. For example, if a complex variant was manually corrected, if candidates were altered or added to reflect transcript annotation issues or observed alternative splicing, if special consideration was given to driver variants, candidates selected based on class II alone, reference matches, etc. If any peptides were determined or corrected by manual work or ad hoc analysis, describe those in detail here along with visualizations if helpful.

Advanced Topics

Neoantigen Candidates from RNA Fusions The immunogenomics pipeline performs RNA fusion calling with STAR-Fusion and runs FusionInspector on the resulting fusion candidates. STAR-Fusion predicted fusions are also annotated with AGfusion and those annotated as having a coding impact are supplied to pVACfuse which attempts to identify neoantigens. Candidate RNA fusions should be manually reviewed using FusionInspector and IGV (e.g. review support from soft clipped reads spanning exon-exon junctions of the fusion). If the fusion support is acceptable (ideally suggesting robust expression), examine pVACfuse results to determine if any high quality neoantigens are predicted.

Fusion Review

Open the fusion inspector html

'/gcp_immuno_workflow/rnaseq/fusioninspector_evidence/finspector.fusion_inspector_web.html', this web page will show possible fusions with evidence. A believable fusion would be one with

- Junction reads + Spanning read counts > 5 and junction reads >= 1
- The fusion is not a read-through
 - Left Chr and Right Chr are different OR chromosome are the same BUT Left Strand and Right Strand are different OR chromosome and strand are the same BUT ABS(Left Pos - Right Pos) < 1,000,000 OR Fusion GeneA Name OR Fusion GeneB Name matches a known fusion driver gene
- The fusion has a large anchor support

Example: GMB119

Fusion	Junction Reads	Spanning Fragments	Splice Type	Left Gene	Left Chr	Left Pos	Left Strand	Right Gene	Right Chr	Right Pos	Right Strand
PSPC1--MRPS31P2	10	2	Includes Reference	PSPC1^ENSG00000121390	chr13	19677724	-	MRPS31P2^ENSG00000232894	chr13	19570288	-
PLCG1--LEUTX	191	18	Includes Reference	PLCG1^ENSG00000124181	chr20	41137858	+	LEUTX^ENSG00000213921	chr19	39784527	+
PLCG1--LEUTX	15	0	Includes Reference	PLCG1^ENSG00000124181	chr20	41137035	+	LEUTX^ENSG00000213921	chr19	39784527	+
PLCG1--LEUTX	3	8	DOES NOT Include Reference	PLCG1^ENSG00000124181	chr20	41137731	+	LEUTX^ENSG00000213921	chr19	39784527	+

The PLCG1::LEUTX fusion candidate mentioned above is predicted to produce two possible transcript fusions:

211.PLCG1_LEUTX.ENST00000244007_ENST00000638280.inframe_fusion.72

210.PLCG1_LEUTX.ENST00000244007_ENST00000396841.frameshift_fusion.72

ID	Best Peptide	Allele	IC50 MT	%ile MT	Expr
211.PLCG1_LEUTX.ENST00000244007_ENST00000638280.inframe_fusion.72	GADKIEGAK	HLA-C*08:0	1520.323	2.3	0.661
213.PLCG1_LEUTX.ENST00000373271_ENST00000638280.inframe_fusion.72	GADKIEGAK	HLA-C*08:0	1520.323	2.3	0.661
215.PLCG1_LEUTX.ENST00000685551_ENST00000638280.inframe_fusion.72	GADKIEGAK	HLA-C*08:0	1520.323	2.3	0.661
210.PLCG1_LEUTX.ENST00000244007_ENST00000396841.frameshift_fusion.72	FGYNGETGF	HLA-C*08:0	2935.029	10	0.661
212.PLCG1_LEUTX.ENST00000373271_ENST00000396841.frameshift_fusion.72	FGYNGETGF	HLA-C*08:0	2935.029	10	0.661
214.PLCG1_LEUTX.ENST00000685551_ENST00000396841.frameshift_fusion.72	FGYNGETGF	HLA-C*08:0	2935.029	10	0.661

The frameshift version is not predicted to lead to a good class I peptide, but the inframe version is predicted to give rise to the following peptide with a percentile rank of 2.3% (for HLA-C*08:02). IGV review of the fusion breakpoints suggests strong support (from soft-clipped reads) on both sides of the fusion in all three tumor regions samples.

Best peptide: GADKIEGAK

The fusion CDS sequence from FusionInspector is:

```
MAGAASPCANGCGPGAPSDAEVLHLCRSLEVGTVMTLFYSKKSQRPERKTFQVKLETRQITWSRGADKIEGAKGPR  
RYRRPRTRFLSKQLTALRELLEKTMHPSLATMGKLASKLQLDLSVVKIWFKNQRAKWKRQQRQMQTRPSLGPAN  
QTTSVKKEETPSAITTANIRPVSPGISDANDHDLREPSGIKNPGGASASARVSSWDSQSYDIEQICLGASNPPWASTL  
FEIDEFVKIYDLPGEDDTSSLNQYLFPVCLEYDQLQSSV*
```

While the fusion is certainly compelling, the best peptide spans the fusion breakpoint by only a single amino acid. "GADKIEGA" match the wild type PLCG1 sequence. The first amino acid on the LEUTX side, an "E" becomes "K" in the fusion product. The rest of the sequence from that point is wildtype LEUTX sequence. In other words the amino acid sequence largely presented to the TCR is mostly just wild type PLCG1 sequence.

MT peptide: GADKIEGAK vs. WT peptide: GADKIEGAE

The mutant and wild type versions of this peptide are not predicted to differ significantly in their binding/presentation. For this reason, this fusion sequence is not a good candidate.

Further examples:

https://pvactools.readthedocs.io/en/latest/pvacview/pvacseq_module/pvacseq_vignette.html

Neoantigen Candidates from Tumor Specific RNA Splicing Events A conservative approach to identifying splice neoantigens is to investigate splicing variants that impact canonical splice acceptor or donor sites (cis regulatory splice variants). In order to consider a candidate of this type the following criteria should be considered.

- A somatic variant is annotated by VEP as a splice variant (or splice region variant)
- The somatic variant is of high quality (passes manual review as described above)
- The tumor RNA-seq data shows clear evidence of a novel splicing pattern (exon skipping or alternative acceptor/donor site usage) that makes sense given the splice variant. For example, a splice acceptor variant is identified and the RNAseq data suggests that the impacted exon is skipped or an alternative upstream or downstream acceptor site variant is used. Note that a single somatic splice variant can lead to more than one tumor specific alternative splicing event.

Assuming the candidate looks good according to these criteria, the protein coding impact of the alternative splicing can be considered. An alternative transcript can be constructed manually, translated, and the "neoORF" can be examined to find novel peptide sequences that can be processed with pVACbind. Depending on the impact of the splice event the neoantigens may correspond to (A) a junction peptide sequence arising from exon skipping and inframe connection of two known exons, (B) a junction peptide arising from alternative acceptor/donor usage that shortens the transcript and leads to an inframe connection, (C) new inframe peptide sequence arising from partial intron inclusion, (D) peptide arising from a frameshift induced by the splicing event.

Note that examination of these impacts and prediction of the neoantigen candidate peptides that may arise has been implemented as pVACsplice (currently in beta).

Peptide Modifications to Improve Solubility or other Manufacturing Considerations It is possible that a peptide manufacturer may need to add non-wildtype amino acids to the N- and/or C- terminal end of

synthetic long peptides to improve their synthesis, stability or solubility characteristics. In these instances the modified peptide sequences should be examined with pVACbind to test whether new strong binding peptides to the patient's HLA alleles are inadvertently created and should be excluded.

Vector Designs The purpose of this step is to prepare a construct that contains all the neoantigen peptide candidates concatenated together with spacers as preferred by a particular manufacturer or as needed to avoid "junctional epitopes". These are novel peptide sequences created by the joining of adjacent candidates. For safety reasons these are screened and any such sequences with strong MHC binding predictions are avoided. To create a vector design without any such sequences we use pVACvector which will iterate over possible alternative orderings of the peptides and test each combination for junctional epitopes to ensure there are none with a predicted binding affinity less than an accepted cutoff (default 500 nm). If no solution can be found, the use of spacers (additional non reference amino acid sequences) is attempted and the iterative process of searching for an optimal ordering is repeated.

The output of pVACvector can be used as input for a DNA, mRNA or adenovirus vaccine delivery platform.